

Fortification of Fruits and Vegetables through Combined Vacuum Impregnation and Dehydration

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ABSTRACT

The enrichment of fruits and vegetables with minerals and vitamins or other physiological active components can be good choice to develop functional foods. Vacuum impregnation allows to introduce controlled quantities of a solution in the porous structure of fruits and vegetables. This solution contains physiological active components, a_w or pH depressors, antimicrobials etc. A process combining vacuum impregnation with a suitable method of drying is a novel concept for developing fortified dried fruits and vegetables. In this paper technology of vacuum impregnation and various methods of drying of fruits and vegetables as well as effect of different dehydration method on quality of the dried products has been discussed.

Key words: Vacuum impregnation, physiological active components, functional foods, dehydration.

INTRODUCTION

Health benefits are one of the specific issues that will greatly influence the food industry in the next few years. Functional foods are products that may provide health benefit beyond the additional content of nutrients or through other added physiologically active components. Fruits and vegetables are increasingly being consumed because of their appreciated nutritional and fresh properties. The enrichment of these products with minerals, vitamins, or other physiologically active components can be a good choice to develop functional foods. Among the technologies used in the development of functional food (FF), vacuum impregnation of porous food matrices with adequate solution / suspensions of PAC has been claimed as a useful way to obtain this kind of products, without destroying the initial food matrix. Vacuum impregnation technique represents a good choice for developing high quality fruit products or food ingredients, taking advantage of their increasing composition, increasing their sweetness and improving their sensory acceptance.

VACUUM IMPREGNATION

Vacuum impregnation of structured foods implies the partial release of gas from pores and its substitution by an external liquid. Therefore impregnation changes in physicochemical and structural properties of foods and these changes affect its behaviour in drying operation. Vacuum impregnation of a porous product consists of exchanging the internal gas or liquid occluded in open pores for an external liquid phase due to the action of hydrodynamic mechanisms (HDM) promoted by pressure changes (Fito, 1994, Fito and Pastor, 1994). The operation is carried out in two steps after the product immersion in the tank containing the liquid phase. In the first step, vacuum pressure ($P_1 < 50-100 \text{ mbar}$) is imposed on the system for a short time (t_1) in the closed tank, thus promoting the expansion and outflow of the product internal gas. The releasing of the gas takes the product pore native liquid with it. In the second step the atmospheric pressure (P_2) is restored in the tank for a time (t_2) and compression leads to a great volume reduction of the remaining gas in the pores and so to the subsequent in flow of the external liquid in the porous structure.

Vacuum impregnation allows a more rapid and controlled

Fig.1. Flow chart to produce Vacuum Impregnated Enriched Dried Fruit products

impregnation of desired solutes in foods. It has been applied to minimally processed fruits (Tapia de Daza, Alzamora, and Welti chanes, 1996;) intermediate moisture products (Tapia de Daza *et al.*, 1996, Martinez-Monzo *et al.*, 1998). However to achieve a better and efficient impregnation, it is required to know the effective porosity of the food in order to predict the theoretical maximum solution that can be impregnated. Knowledge of the impregnation behaviour of the food under diverse vacuum impregnation conditions is essential to design some preservation processes. Calcium fortification of vegetables by applying vacuum impregnation is an alternative in developing functional foods. Nevertheless, calcium ions can interact with the plant tissues, modifying its mechanical and vacuum impregnation responses.

OSMOTIC DEHYDRATION

Osmotic dehydration (OD) has recently received attention as an intermediate step in drying, dehydration and freeze drying of fruits (Ponting of fruits (Ponting 1966, Ponting, 1973). The phenomenon of osmosis is utilized in the dehydration of food products. The process of osmosis can be used to remove water from a dilute solution contained within a semi permeable membrane by surrounding the membrane with a more concentrated solution. Water diffuses through the membrane from the dilute to the concentrated solution until the equilibrium concentration is reached. Membrane of greater solute rejection lead to the concept of membrane coat around the item to be dehydrated. So the process of dehydration of membrane coated food by osmosis was developed. Calcium pectate membrane has given best results.

The main principle involved in osmotic dehydration is the partial dehydration of fruits and vegetables by osmosis comparatively at lower temperature and thus reduce the severity of thermal treatment in the production of dehydrated product which would be very near to natural with respect to color flavor, taste and texture. Sugar syrup has a protective effect on color, flavor through out the dehydration process. This makes it possible to produce dried fruits of high quality.

Since any plant or animal tissue acts as a semi permeable membrane, they can be dehydrated osmotically by immersion in a strong solution of sugar or salt in water. OD is therefore equally applicable to fruits or vegetables, meat and fishes. The osmotically dehydrated fruit after which it is drained and dried further in air or vacuum dryer reduces the fruit to about 50% of

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its original weight. This makes it possible to produce dried products of high quality with little or without use of SO₂ (Fig. 1).

Recently the OD of mango, banana and many other fruits have been studied and it is found that OD is one of the cheap and simple methods of preserving tropical fruits (Hope and Vital, 1972). Process steps in osmotic dehydration, driven forces and phenomena responsible for changes in the system in stage of free energy are given in Table 1 (Pedro Fito *et al.*, 2001).

TABLE 1: Various Applications of PEF in the Preservation of Foods.

Process step	Time range	Driven force	Dissipative free energy phenomena	Storage free energy phenomena
Impregnation (capillary VI)	Minutes	Pressure gradients	Flow of external liquid	Volume reduction (gas phase)
Osmotic dehydration	Hours	Chemical potential of components (mainly water)	Water loss Solid gain Plasmolysis* Liquid flow through cell wall	Deformation of cellular matrix
Impregnation	Days	Pressure gradients	Relaxation of cellular network, Flow of external fluid	Equilibrium

*In osmotic process where no vacuum impregnation (VI) with osmotic solution has been carried out these phenomena occur coupled with the relaxation of shrunk cellular network in the next impregnation step (Fito *et al.*, 1999a).

Advantages of Osmotic Dehydration

There are number of advantages of OD process which are stated below (Ponting *et al.*, 1966, Dixon *et al.*, 1977, Islam and Flink 1982, Chaudhari *et al.*, 1993).

- It minimizes the effect of temperature on food quality and preserves the wholesomeness of the food, as no high temperature/phase change is required in the process.
- Mild heat treatment favors color, flavor and vitamins retention resulting in the product having superior organoleptic characteristics.
- The process needs no artificial preservatives.
- The process is quite simple, economical and does not require any sophisticated equipments.
- The process is economically viable for highly perishable fruits.
- A suitable osmotic agent could be useful for new product formulation.
- It prevents enzymatic browning and inhibits activities of polyphenol oxidase.
- It improves texture and rehydration properties.
- Acid removal and sugar uptake by fruit modifies the composition and improves the taste and acceptability which is called candying effect.
- Constant immersion of products in osmotic agents avoids the use of CO₂ resulting in a product with better color.
- It protects against the structural collapse of the product during subsequent drying.
- It minimizes the damages of cellular tissues.
- Osmo-convective dried products are suitable for storage in the atmosphere of considerable humidity without any threat of caking.

Vacuum Osmotic Dehydration (VOD)

When pressure is lower than atmospheric pressure is used, the vacuum OD occurs. It has been studied for several fruits and vegetables (Mata, 1991, Fito, 1993, Fito *et al.*, 1993b).

Several advantages are observed for VOD: a faster kinetics principally during the first period of drying, and a sugar gain similar to that obtained for OD. In fruits the product obtained by VOD shows better sensorial properties than achieved at the same temperature by OD. Also the former shows more stability in relation to deteriorative reactions (browning and oxidation) (Pastor *et al.*, 1992, Fito, 1993; Mata, 1991).

DEHYDRATION OF FRUITS

Dried fruits and vegetables are an important food sector. Most fruits and vegetables are generally dried conventionally with

heated air. Hot air dried fruits and vegetables are often difficult to rehydrate because of case hardening and shrinkage during the drying process.

Today the potential for dehydration is greater than ever. Much has been done to improve the quality of dehydrated foods. Among the things that had led to improvement are the use of raw materials better adapted to the requirements of dehydration, new processing technologies, more careful application of known processing procedures as well as sophisticated quality control procedures, improved equipments, lower moisture content in finished products, better control of sulfur application and improved packaging.

Dehydration is one of the oldest methods of food preservation that represents a very important aspect of food processing. Dehydration refers to the use of mechanical equipments and artificial heating methods under carefully controlled condition of temperature, humidity and airflow. Although the term 'Dehydrated' does not refer to any specific moisture in the finished product, it is usually considered to imply virtually complete water removal to a range of 1-5% moisture. Products with such low water content can be stored at room temperature for periods well in excess of 2 years without detectable change in quality and indications are that most low moisture fruits will remain acceptable for periods of 5 years or more when stored under temperate conditions (about 65°F) in moisture-proof containers.

Dehydration includes the application of artificial heat to vaporize water and some means of removing water vapor after its separation from the fruit tissues. The removal of water involves mass transfer and the application of heat in some manner also involves heat transfer. Energy must be supplied to vaporize the water and to remove the resultant water vapor from the drying surface. The quantity of heat energy required to vaporize water depends upon the temperature at which vaporization occurs. Thermal damage incurred to a product during drying is directly proportional to the temperature and time involved.

Advantages of Properly Dehydrated Fruits

1. They have longer shelf life under proper storage conditions because a high degree of inhibition of bacteria, enzymatic and mold action is achieved.
2. They have substantially lower transportation, handling and storage costs and do not require costly refrigeration during transport and storage.
3. Dehydration hardly affects the main calorie-providing constituents of fruits. It leaves the mineral contents virtually unchanged. Therefore, the process is helpful in preserving the nutritive content of the final product. Vitamin losses are no greater with dehydration than with other preservation methods, and low moisture food can be conveniently fortified with vitamins.
4. They provide a consistent product and important modern marketing requirement. Seasonal variation in product quality is either absent or at a minimum with low moisture fruits.
5. They provide opportunities for maximum convenience, flexibility and economics as industrial or foodservice ingredients because they can be sized, shaved, formed, etc., to fit almost any requirement, with low moisture fruits. the purchaser uses all that he buys thus eliminating waste disposal and pollution problems. Further, they go a long way towards attaining price stability throughout the year.
6. They utilize the most economical and disposal form of packaging. The two major considerations in packaging dried fruits are the exclusion of moisture and oxygen.
7. They offer many distinctive conveniences as snack products.

MICROWAVE DRYING

Microwave is electromagnetic radiation indicated in the spectrum between ultrahigh frequency and infrared frequency. This includes frequencies between 300 Mhz to 300 GHz. Microwave energy is not a form of heat. Heat is a secondary effect of a electromagnetic field interacting with matter, such as food. The microwave field changes direction millions of time per second in microwave oven. The conversion of microwave

energy into heat is explained by basically two phenomena:

- Molecule, with a permanent dipolar moment, rotates in the rapidly changing electric field. When molecules rotate in a field that changes its polarity at a frequency of many millions of time per second, heat is evolved because of friction forces between the molecules.
- Charge drift under the action of the field (ionic conduction). When the ions drift, due to the electric field, they collide with other molecules in a billiard ball fashion and heat is evolved because of friction.

Water molecules are polar, i.e. the center of charge is displaced. This means that they can rotate under the influence of an alternating electric field. Foodstuff usually contains 50-97% water. Thus food is very well suited for heating and drying with microwave energy. In hot air drying, the product surface becomes dry first and dried food layer is a poor conductor of heat throughout the dehydration process. Microwaves, however, are able to penetrate a dry surface layer and heat the food throughout all highmolecules regions. This promotes mass transport and increases drying rate.

Microwave drying offers an alternate way to improve the quality of dehydrated products. Microwave drying system combines microwave and convectional heating. The heating may take place in separate operation or simultaneously. Microwave drying, like convectional drying, is caused by water vapor pressure differences between interior and surface regions, which provide a driving force for moisture transfer. It is most effective at product moisture content below 20% (Mudgett, 1989; Giese, 1992). Microwave energy should be applied in the falling rate period or at a low moisture content (where conventional drying takes a long time) to finish drying. Microwave drying has been used in drying of herbs (Giese, 1992), potato (Bouraout *et al.*, 1994), raisins (Kostaropoulos and Saravacos, 1995), apple and mushroom (Funebo and Ohlsson, 1998), diced apples (Feng and Tang, 1998), carrots (Prabhanjan, Ramaswamy and Raghavan, 1995, Litvin, Mannheim, and Miltz, 1998; Lin, Durance and Scaman, 1998) and banana (Maskan, 2000).

Microwave heating resulted in greater increase in drying rates, almost 13-14 times higher compared to that with hot air drying at the start of the drying process. Shrinkage took place during drying by all the drying methods and it was calculated using.

$$S = \frac{V}{V_0}$$

S = Shrinkage
V = Volume of sample (ml) at anytime
V₀ = Initial volume of sample (ml)

The shrinkage of kiwifruit samples was 85%, 81% and 76%, for microwave, hot air and hot air-microwave drying, respectively. Hot air drying promoted a moderate shrinkage, which was explained by the fact that a long drying time gives more time for the product to shrink (Ratti, 1994). The shrinkage was the least by combined drying method. However, there was a higher and rapid shrinkage of samples dried by microwave. It is because of extensive heat generation, accelerating removal of water from the tissue in the sample by microwave.

Most vegetables and fruits are generally dried convectively with heated air. Hot air dried vegetables are often difficult to rehydrate because of case hardening and shrinkage during the drying process. The combined use of microwave and convective drying not only greatly enhances the drying rate, but may also improve the final product quality (Torrington, Van, Dijk, and Bartels, 1996).

Microwave energy can successfully be applied in several unit processes in the food industry because of the resulting volumetric heating of the material. There is no need for a driving temperature gradient; the practically obtained power densities are generally much higher compared to conventional heat transfer. The high thermal efficiency of microwave at low moisture content gives a possibility for decreasing energy consumption in comparison with convective drying process (Nijhuis *et al.*, 1996) because of the internally generated high water vapor pressure, it can result in a more porous product, which gives a good alternative for the poorly reconstituting vegetables used in different food stuffs.

General advantages for the application of electromagnetic energy in fruits and vegetables are thoroughly investigated (Nijhuis *et al.*, 1998) and can be listed as follows:

- More efficient drying in the falling rate period/reduction of drying time.
 - Rapid energy dissipation throughout the material/uniform heating.
 - Easy to combine with other drying techniques.
 - Selective heating of the center with suitable product properties.
 - Over drying/high surface temperature can be prevented.
 - Possibility for puffing the material.
 - Lower product temperature in combination with a vacuum treatment.
 - Minor migration of water constituents.
 - Possibility for energy savings.
- Other motivations for applying combined osmotic and microwave dehydration as a pretreatment is:
- More efficient drying in the falling rate period/reduction of drying time.
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 - Lower product temperature in combination with a vacuum treatment.
 - Minor migration of water constituents.
 - Possibility for energy savings.
- Other motivations for applying combined osmotic and microwave dehydration as a pretreatment is:
- Possibility to produce unique product with better taste.
 - Improved flavor characteristics and/or increased nutritional value.
 - Prevention of oxidation of the product and color stabilization.
 - Improvement of the texture of the product such as higher final bulk volume of the product compared to heated air dehydration or microwave dehydration.

The advantages of using microwave energy in the drying of carrots were described by Torrington *et al.*, 1996. The more homogeneous dehydration and the developed internal pressure with microwaves results in less reduction in the volume of the microwave dried product. Also the volume of air within the product is higher in the microwave-treated carrot than in air-dried products with the same bulk volume.

The drawbacks of microwave heating in general are:

- The problems of uneven heating. Too high temperature in the edges and corners of products may lead to overheating and irreversible drying out. The customers will experience this as low quality of the product.
- A way of controlling the mass transport by controlling the power input that is needed, as too rapid mass transport may cause damage to the food texture by 'puffing'.
- High starts up costs have prevented many potential users of microwave energy from investing in the new technology.
- Previously, operational costs were more as expensive magnetrons needed to be replaced too frequently.

INFRARED DRYING

Infrared radiation lies between the visible and microwave portion of the electromagnetic spectrum. Infrared waves have wavelength longer than visible and shorter than microwave, and have frequencies, which are lower than visible and higher than microwave. The electromagnetic spectrums within infrared wavelengths are broken into three categories: near (4-1000 nm), medium (2-4 mm) and far (0.7-2 mm) infrared. Near infrared refers to the part of infrared spectrum that is closest to visible light and far infrared refers to the part that is closer to microwave region. Medium infrared is the region between these two.

The primary source of infrared is heat or thermal radiation.

This is the radiation produced by the motion of atoms and molecules in an object. The higher the temperature, greater the movements of atoms and molecules and more infrared radiations they produce. Any object which has temperature above absolute zero (-459.67°F or -273.15°C or 0° Kelvin) radiates in the infrared range.

Infrared heating of food is also gaining popularity because of the simplicity of construction and operation. Its transient response, significant energy savings over other thermal processes and ease of constructions of hybrid system with convective and conductive heating sources (Sandhu, 1986) are other features. Infrared dryers provide high rate of energy input to the material to a depth, which depends on the nature of the material and the wavelength of the incident radiation (Zubicinski *et al.*, 1992).

Advantages of Infrared Heating

Electric infrared heating has many benefits over the convectional heating. The important among them are:

Improved Quality due to Non-Contact Heating

Infrared emitters can heat a product without physical contact between them or without the necessity of a medium like air having to with contact the object. It can also heat in vacuum. This is advantageous where dust and other contaminants can mar the product's finish.

High-Energy Efficiency

In infrared heating the heat lost to air or to surrounding is very small. Also, infrared light can be focused on the object. Hence energy efficiency is high.

Fast Response of the Emitters

Because of low thermal inertia of emitters there is no need for long preheat period. Quartz short wave infrared system is practically instant ON-OFF type.

Faster Heat Shorter Time Cycles

Infrared reduces the heating time cycles to typically one third of those required in convection ovens. Infrared heats the product directly without heating the medium in between. In case of coating, infrared even penetrates the entire thickness of coating instantly. This makes it a fast and one stage heat transfer.

Low Initial Cost

Because of simple and compact construction, infrared heating system typically has lower initial cost.

High Long-Term Benefits

Electric infrared is much more efficient as compared to other sources of heat such as kerosene oil. Hence, even though electricity is costlier per unit of energy, the actual running cost is comparable to other heating systems.

Flexibility

Infrared heating can be installed for any type of material movement - vertical, horizontal, inclined etc. It can even be installed on bends, radii etc. in case of space constraints. They can be installed in very short times and subsequent additions for higher production are easy because of modular construction.

FREEZE DRYING

In conventional vacuum drying, moisture in the foods is converted from the liquid to the vapor phase. Freeze drying is far more expensive than convective drying and is used for the production of a minor amount of high value arable and horticultural products. In this method of removal of water, the product is frozen and the temperature maintained below the triple point of the constituent aqueous solution so that the water vapor can be sublimed from the frozen solution. There is, therefore, a direct transfer from solid to vapor phase without the liquid phase. The process is carried out under vacuum to provide a high vapor diffusion potential and is accelerated by supplying heat in some convenient form either radiant, conductive or from microwaves (Holdsworth, 1971). It is generally considered as dehydration procedure that produces a dried product of the highest quality and therefore is potentially an extremely attractive method.

The advantages of freeze drying are high flavor retention; maximum retention of nutritional value; minimal damage to product structure and texture; very little change in shape, color, and appearance; and finished products with an open structure that permits fast and complete rehydration. The bulk density of the freeze-dried materials was increased with temperature. The disadvantages of the process include high capital investment; high processing costs; and the need for special packaging to avoid oxidation and moisture pickup in finished products.

The freeze-drying process involves two basic steps. The raw fruit is first frozen in the conventional manner and then dried to around 2% moisture in a vacuum chamber. The freezing rate may affect the reconstitution property of freeze-dried foods because the porous nature of the product is controlled by this factor. The process of vapor removal is influenced by the size, shape and tortuosity of the pores. In general, the faster the freezing rate, the smaller the voids, and the slower the freezing-drying rate the bigger the voids (Karel, 1963).

The most common type of freeze drying equipment is a batch chamber system similar to a vacuum shelf drier but with special feature to meet the needs of the freeze drying process. The material to be dried is placed on trays arranged between the heated plates. The plates are either electrically heated or internally heated with steam, pressurized hot water or oil. Before heat is applied, a vacuum must be drawn in the chamber. The vacuum is produced either with a mechanical pump or with steam ejectors. Rapid evacuation of the chamber is essential once the product is loaded to ensure that there is no thawing before freeze-drying is started. The vacuum system must maintain a pressure under 1 Torr so that the product remains frozen as long as water is present during the drying cycle.

Refrigerated condensers are usually applied to condense the vapor that is removed from the product. The surface of the refrigerated condenser must be maintained at a lower temperature than the ice within the product to ensure mass transfer. To improve the storage stability of freeze dried fruits, it is a common practice at the completion of the drying process to break the vacuum in the chamber with nitrogen gas, thereby preventing the instantaneous absorption of oxygen by the open pores of the dried product. The nitrogen-impregnated product is then packed under nitrogen in airtight, moisture proof containers.

A great deal of research has focused to improve heat transfer during freeze-drying. The early technique of supplying heat by conduction from plates to food placed between them restricted vapor flow and also provided uneven contact. To overcome this problem expanded metal inserts are used between the plates and metals. This process is referred as 'accelerated freeze drying', and described in detail by Hanson (1961).

To improve the efficiency of the freeze-drying process, multiple batch chamber operation is employed by some plants. Continuous systems have also been designed (Togashi and Mercer 1966). Considerable attention is being given to hybrid schemes that take advantages of the positive effect of freeze drying on the cellular structure of food but reduce the cost of the process by removing some of the moisture before freezing or freeze drying (Anon. 1982).

Freeze drying is applicable to a wide range of fruit products. The major problem is its very high cost compared with the costs of canning, freezing or other dehydration methods. Freeze drying has proved to be the superior method of dehydration for many common foods, including blue berries, cherries and strawberries (Anon. 1982).

Freeze drying produces the highest quality dried food products. This is largely because the structure of the food is not severely damaged as in other preservation procedures, therefore, technological progress in freeze drying will concern two major fields:

- The reduction of running costs by increasing the process efficiency (Reduction of the freeze-drying time, optimization of the operating parameters).
- The processing of new products that require a high final quality.

EFFECT OF DIFFERENT METHODS OF DEHYDRATION ON THE QUALITY OF THE DRIED PRODUCTS

The properties of dried fruits and vegetables are influenced by chemical and physical changes. Chemical changes mainly affect sensory properties such as color, taste and aroma, whereas physical properties such as swelling capacity and cooking time. Heat treatment of fruits and vegetables often reduces the number of original volatile flavor compounds, while introducing additional volatile flavor compounds through the auto-oxidation, thermal decomposition, and/or initiation of Maillard reaction. After drying, volatile compounds are partially retained in the dried products.

Although air drying is the most popular commercial drying technique to preserve perishable products, as it is relatively inexpensive, this technique is considered to give less satisfactory product quality than other conservation procedures both with respect to the nutritional value and to the sensory properties such as texture, color and flavor. However, the quality may be improved by pretreatments such as direct osmosis or optimization of the processing conditions.

Though quality improvement by innovation in drying technology have been reported, extensive sensory studies on dehydrated fruits and vegetables are scarce. The flavor and textural characteristics of hot air dried and freeze-dried French beans, peas and spinach were compared by means of flavor and texture profiling (Sinesio *et al.*, 1995). It was found that the sensory panel clearly detected benefits of the freeze-drying process over traditional air-drying of the vegetables. The samples were rehydrated before presenting to the assessors. The freeze-dried products, which received high scores for juiciness and fruity aroma, were natural in color and texture. The air-dried products were characterized by an unnatural color, texture and had a burnt and bitter flavor.

Combined microwave-vacuum drying of banana slices resulted in higher quality products than freeze-drying. However, no substantial differences were observed in color, taste, aroma, texture and rehydration capacity (Drouzes 1996).

Other studies also reported the high quality of microwave processed products. In a separate study, the flavor of ripe bananas dried with microwaves was preferred over a warm air-dried product. Microwave-assisted drying of carrot cubes resulted in a substantial decrease in drying time and the product was better than for conventionally air-dried samples. Relative advantages and disadvantages of several dry conservation processes are presented in Table 2 (Nijhuis, H. H. *et al.*, 1998).

TABLE 2: Relative Advantages and Disadvantages of Several Dry Conservation Processes. (Nijhuis, H. H. *et al.*, 1998)

Characteristics	Freeze Drying	Microwave	Infra Red
Drying rate	-	+	+
Flexibility	-	+	+
Start-up time	0	0	0
Reliability	0	-	0
Investment costs	--	-	0
Energy consumption	+	0	0
Running costs	+	0	0
Color	++	+	+
Flavor	++	+	+
Nutritional value	++	+	+
Microbial stability	-	+	+
Enzyme inactivation	-	+	+
Mechanical stability	--	-	-
Rehydration capacity	++	+	+
Crispness	++	+	+
Fresh-like appearance	++	+	+

Rating: -- strongly negative; - negative; 0 no effect; + positive; ++ strongly positive All ratings are indicate the effect of using an alternative technology instead of hot air drying on specific process or quality characteristics.

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